

A nodalization study on modeling the containment and reactor pool of an integral PWR

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of nodalization of the containment and reactor pool of a small integral Pressurized Water Reactor (iPWR) using the MELCOR 2.2 code. The research focuses on Design 1 of the EU-funded SASPAM-SA project, featuring a containment partially submerged in the reactor pool. Two accident scenarios were analyzed: a Design Basis Accident (DBA) and a severe accident. The simulations were conducted with four different nodalizations: a detailed base model, a single-volume containment model, a single-volume pool model, and a single-volume model for both the containment and the pool. The results indicate that while detailed nodalization can simulate temperature stratification, its effect on the overall accident simulation results, pressures and fission product releases is limited. The findings suggest that differences between single-volume and more detailed nodalizations are relatively small, with the detailed nodalization providing slightly lower containment pressures during the DBA scenario due to more efficient heat transfer.

1. Introduction

An integral PWR (iPWR) is a type of Small Modular Reactor (SMR), characterized by the integration of the entire primary circuit and the steam generators within the Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV). The EU-funded SASPAM-SA (Safety Analysis of SMR with Passive Mitigation Strategies – Severe Accident) project addresses the capability of accident analysis codes to simulate phenomena characterizing the containment behavior of iPWRs. Two generic design concepts are considered in the project. Design 1 has a containment partially submerged in the reactor pool and an electric power of about 60 MW. Design 2 has a dry containment and an electric power of about 300 MW. This paper concerns Design 1.

iPWRs bring new challenges to accident simulations. In particular, the entire RPV–containment–pool system becomes tightly coupled, thanks to the absence of thermal insulation around the RPV, and the small size and the external cooling of the submerged containment. Modeling this coupled thermal–hydraulic system is essential for analyzing the efficiency of passive decay heat removal. (Mascari et al., 2023).

The purpose of this paper is to study how results of iPWR accident simulations are affected by the nodalization of the containment and of the reactor pool that surrounds the containment. The simulations were performed with the MELCOR 2.2 code (Humphries et al., 2021). Two

accident scenarios were considered: one design basis accident (DBA), and one severe accident. Both scenarios were calculated with four different nodalizations: the detailed *base* model, the *1-vol cont.* model with the containment modeled as a single control volume, the *1-vol pool* model with the reactor pool modeled as a single volume, and the *1-vol both* model with both the containment and the reactor pool modeled as single volumes. The initial and boundary conditions were the same in all four models.

Chapter 2 of this paper introduces issues related to dividing open regions, such as the containment and the reactor pool, into several control volumes. Avoiding these issues is the reason why it would be desirable to model the containment and the pool as single control volumes. Chapter 3 describes the MELCOR model. The results with the base model are then compared with the simpler single-volume models in chapters 4 and 5, dealing with the DBA and the severe accident scenario, respectively. Chapter 6 collects the conclusions.

2. Issues with dividing open regions into several control volumes

Containments are often nodalized so that each compartment is associated with one control volume. However, sometimes it is necessary to model stratification within a compartment, which requires dividing it into several control volumes. This causes many challenges for lumped parameter codes, such as MELCOR.

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Nomenclature

AC	Alternating Current
CNL	Canadian Nuclear Laboratories
CVCS	Chemical and Volume Control System
DBA	Design Basis Accident
EU	European Union
iPWR	Integral Pressurized Water Reactor
LOCA	Loss Of Coolant Accident
NRC	Nuclear Regulatory Commission
OECD NEA	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, Nuclear Energy Agency
PSI	Paul Scherrer Institut
PWR	Pressurized Water Reactor
RPV	Reactor Pressure Vessel
RRV	Reactor Recirculation Valve
RSV	Reactor Safety Valve
RVV	Reactor Vent Valve
SA	Severe Accident
SASPAM-SA	Safety Analysis of SMR with Passive Mitigation Strategies – Severe Accident
SMR	Small Modular Reactor

Dividing compartments into multiple control volumes introduces a user effect: different code users obtain different results simply due to different nodalizations. Designing a proper nodalization requires a prior understanding of the expected stratification and flow patterns. Inexperienced users can easily create non-physical nodalizations. A typical mistake is dead-end volumes, for example, a stack of control volumes without any radial nodalization, leading to complete stratification and ignorance of convection flows.

Dividing compartments into several volumes easily leads to errors in the input deck, as the complexity increases. The user needs to manually define a volume–altitude table and initial conditions for every control volume. If the main flow direction is not vertical, the user needs to override the default control volume area. And for every flow path, the user needs to define opening elevations and heights, segment areas, lengths and hydraulic diameters, inertial lengths, momentum exchange lengths, loss coefficients, and possible bubble rise models. The containment nodalization with 18 control volumes and 22 flow paths applied in this work requires the user to set 403 numbers in the input deck, not counting the heat structure input. Setting so many numbers without errors and checking their correctness is challenging.

Many required flow path parameters are difficult to determine if an open region is divided into several control volumes. The opening heights of vertical flow paths “have no rigorous interpretation” (Humphries et al., 2021). The flow area of a radial flow path is not constant, but it increases when going farther away from the centerline. Still, the user must specify a single flow area. There is no guidance on how to determine the loss coefficients of flow paths that represent an open surface separating two control volumes.

Vertically stacked control volumes tend to generate “levitating” pools. If water is introduced to a control volume, it forms a pool at the bottom of the volume. Then it drains to the lower volume and forms a pool there. And so on, until the code calculates a tiny amount of water levitating at the bottom of every volume. This problem can be alleviated, but not eliminated, by using the heat structure film tracking model, choosing the flow path opening heights smartly, and setting the momentum exchange lengths to zero. Besides cutting the time step and slowing down the calculation, the levitating pools affect aerosol deposition because they block user-defined settling paths from upper to lower volumes, and instead deposit the aerosols to the tiny pool in the upper volume.

Fig. 1. Nodalization of the reactor with 19 volumes. The arrows are flow paths, and the core area is drawn with the orange color. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

A similar issue is encountered if gas is introduced (through a submerged pipe or by boiling on a heat structure surface) to a water pool that is divided into several control volumes. In this case, the gas tends to form tiny layers on the top of each volume. This cuts the time step, slowing down the calculation sometimes seriously. It also affects the pool scrubbing model, which does not understand that the same bubbles rise through all the stacked control volumes.

Dividing compartments into several volumes complicates analyzing the results. The user needs to inspect a very large number of plot variables in order to understand the results and to determine if they are realistic.

Modeling compartments as single control volumes, instead of using a finer nodalization, would avoid the issues discussed above.

3. Plant model

The MELCOR input was developed by VTT, based on the design 1 specifications of the SASPAM-SA project.

3.1. Reactor model

The reactor core consists of 37 PWR fuel assemblies, with an active fuel length of 2 m. In the Core package of MELCOR, the active core was modeled with 3 radial rings and 5 axial levels. In addition, a fourth radial ring represents the space below the downcomer, two axial levels are below the core, and one axial level above the core. The MELCOR best practices (Ross et al., 2014) were followed as well as possible. The default conservative steel oxidation correlation was replaced with the best-estimate correlation (Sevón, 2024).

Fig. 1 presents the thermal–hydraulic nodalization of the reactor. The lower plenum was modeled as a single volume. The core was divided into two volumes: the inner volume represents core rings 1 and 2, while the outer volume represents ring 3. The dT/dz model of the Core

Fig. 2. Containment nodalization with 16 volumes. The arrows are flow paths.

package simulates the vertical fluid temperature distribution within the control volumes. The bypass volume represents the coolant holes inside the reflector. The riser was divided into inner and outer volumes in the same way as the core, in order to model the possible natural circulation between the riser and the core. It is expected that if the water level is below the riser turn, a natural circulation may occur, in which warmer water or steam flows upwards in the center, while cooler water or steam flows downwards in the periphery. This can be modeled with the applied nodalization. In the vertical direction, the riser was divided into three levels. In addition, the riser turn was modeled as a separate volume, collecting the flows from the riser and leading to the steam generators. The pressurizer was modeled as a single volume. The Reactor Safety Valves (RSVs) and the Reactor Vent Valves (RVVs) discharge from the pressurizer to the containment.

The primary side of the steam generators was divided into four volumes in the vertical direction. The downcomer below the steam generators was divided into three volumes, so that the lowest volume is at the core level, while the middle volume extends up to the Reactor Recirculation Valves (RRVs). It is expected that if the RRVs are open, the temperature in the middle volume may be much lower than in the upper volume because cooler water flows from the containment through the RRVs.

Heat transfer through the RPV wall is important because the vessel is not thermally insulated and because in many accident scenarios, water would be in contact with the outer surface. A large number of heat structures are needed in order to reduce the errors caused by the 1-dimensional modeling of partially submerged structures, as the water level changes on both sides of the vessel wall. The RPV wall was modeled as 18 heat structures.

In the secondary side, the feedwater line was modeled as one volume, the steam generator tubes were modeled as four volumes, and the steam line was modeled as one volume. The feedwater source and the steam sink (turbine) were modeled as time-independent volumes. For the steam generator tube heat structures, the helical steam generator heat

Fig. 3. Reactor pool nodalization with 12 volumes. The arrows are flow paths.

transfer correlations were used for the inner surface and the Zukauskas correlation for the outer surface (Humphries et al., 2021).

3.2. Containment model

It seems common to model this kind of containment vessels with two radial rings. This is the case in the models of the NRC (Campbell et al., 2019), Canadian Nuclear Laboratories (Morreale, 2022), and Paul Scherrer Institut (Malicki & Lind, 2024). This is natural, since the inner part is expected to be warmer because it receives heat from the RPV walls. The outer part is expected to be cooler because the outer surface of the containment wall is cooled by the reactor pool. A two-ring nodalization can simulate the radial temperature differences and the resulting natural convection flows. A two-ring nodalization was applied also in the base model of this paper, see Fig. 2.

The CNL and PSI models apply the two-ring nodalization only in the “middle” levels of their nodalization, but have only one volume in the lowermost and uppermost levels. This practice tends to result in more efficient mixing. But lumped parameter codes have a tendency to “overmix”, i.e. underestimate stratification (OECD/NEA, 1999). In order to counteract the overmixing, the two-ring nodalization was applied for all the axial levels.

Some temperature differences in the containment are expected in the vertical direction. The number of levels varies when modeling this kind of containments: the NRC model has 4 levels (Campbell et al., 2019), the CNL model has 5 levels (Morreale, 2022), and the PSI model has 7 levels (Malicki & Lind, 2024). In this work, the base containment nodalization has 8 levels (Fig. 2), so that the lowest 6 levels follow the reactor nodalization (Fig. 1).

The form loss coefficients of all containment flow paths were set to the default value, one, because there are various obstacles that cause changes of flow area and direction. The opening heights of the vertical flow paths were set to 10 cm because that setting usually results in a reasonable drainage of water from upper to lower volumes. The momentum exchange lengths were set to zero, in order to minimize the levitating pool issue described in chapter 2.

Heat transfer through the containment steel wall is important because the outer surface is cooled by the reactor pool. A large number of heat structures is needed in order to reduce the errors caused by the one-dimensional modeling of partially submerged structures, as the water level changes on both sides of the containment wall. The wall was modeled as 22 heat structures.

Containment leakage was modeled from the top of the containment, above the reactor pool water level. The flow path area was set to 0.0802

Fig. 4. Reactor pressure in the DBA scenario.

Fig. 5. Containment pressure in the DBA scenario.

mm² and hydraulic diameter to 0.3 mm. The open fraction of the flow path was adjusted so that it increases linearly from zero at 0.1 MPa to one at 8.65 MPa. This model results in a leak rate of 0.2 % of the containment volume per day at 6.85 MPa for dry air at 21 °C.

3.3. Reactor pool model

The reactor pool is commonly modeled with two stacks of control volumes: the warmer stack representing the bay where the containment resides, and the cooler stack representing the part of the pool that is farther away. The number of levels in the stacks varies: the NRC model has 8 levels (Campbell et al., 2019), while the CNL and the PSI models have 4 levels (Morreale, 2022; Malicki & Lind, 2024). In this work, the base pool nodalization has 6 levels (Fig. 3), following the elevations of the containment nodalization (Fig. 2). The environment was modeled as a time-independent control volume, connected to the reactor building with a large, 0.1 m² flow path, assuming that the building is not leak-tight.

The form loss coefficients of the flow paths in the reactor pool were left to the default values, one, except for the vertical paths in the “cool” stack. Their loss coefficients were set to zero because there are no sudden changes of flow area or direction in the pool. Similarly to the containment model, the opening heights of the vertical flow paths were set to 10 cm, and the momentum exchange lengths were set to zero.

4. DBA scenario

The Design Basis Accident scenario involves a leak from the down-comer to the containment through the CVCS (Chemical and Volume

Fig. 6. Containment gas temperatures in the DBA scenario, base model vs. 1-vol cont. model.

Control System) discharge line. A loss of AC power was assumed at the same time, causing a loss of feedwater. The assumed leak area is 1.45 cm². The leak inlet is 3.5 m above the top of active fuel. The leak outlet is 2.272 m above the inlet, ensuring that it remains above the containment water level, preventing back-flow of water to the reactor. The reactor vent valves and recirculation valves (RVV and RRV) are assumed to operate normally. This is the same scenario that is designated as “DBA 10 %” in (Malicki & Lind, 2024). However, the plant models have been developed completely independently.

The water leak from the reactor causes the containment pressure to increase and the reactor pressure to decrease. Reactor scram is triggered by high containment pressure at 24 s. The opening of the RVVs and RRVs is triggered by low pressure difference between the reactor and the containment at 94 min. Water flows from the containment back to the reactor through the RRVs. The resulting natural circulation transfers the decay heat from the reactor through the containment to the reactor pool, and the water level stabilizes about 3 m above the top of active fuel.

The reactor pressure is plotted in Fig. 4 and the containment pressure in Fig. 5. The reactor pressure turns to increase at 10 min because the water in the core begins to boil. The 1-vol pool model gives the same pressures as the base model. The 1-vol both model gives the same pressures as the 1-vol cont. model. Thus, modeling the reactor pool as a single control volume had no discernible effect on the pressures.

Modeling the containment as a single control volume gives slightly higher containment pressures than the base nodalization. As a result, reactor scram is triggered by high containment pressure slightly earlier (at 15 s with the 1-vol cont. model, vs. 24 s with the more detailed containment nodalization). The earlier scram causes the slightly lower

Fig. 7. Pool temperatures in the DBA scenario, base model vs. 1-vol pool model.

Fig. 8. Reactor water level in the SA scenario, base model.

reactor pressures.

The reason for the higher containment pressures with the 1-vol containment model is less efficient heat transfer to the containment walls. The more detailed nodalization generates natural convection flows in the containment. As a result, the code calculates forced convection heat transfer to the containment walls in the beginning of the accident. If the containment is modeled as a single control volume, the flow velocity within the volume remains close to zero, the heat transfer mode is natural convection, and the heat transfer coefficient is lower.

The base model calculates some stratification of the containment atmosphere, as illustrated in Fig. 6. At 6 h, the difference between the hottest and the coldest control volume is about 14 °C. The temperature calculated by the 1-vol cont. model is within the temperature range of the more detailed model. The peak temperature at the time of the RVV and RRV opening is cropped out to improve the visibility of the curves. The peak temperatures are around 300 °C.

The base model calculates some stratification of the reactor pool, as illustrated in Fig. 7. At 6 h, the lowest two levels are 7–9 °C cooler than the upper levels. The temperature difference between the warmer stack of control volumes adjacent to the containment and the cooler stack farther away (see nodalization in Fig. 3) is very small. The temperature calculated by the 1-vol pool model is the average of the temperatures calculated by the finer nodalization.

Fig. 9. Hydrogen generation in the SA scenario, base model, five calculations to show the numerical noise.

5. Severe accident scenario

The severe accident (SA) scenario involves a spurious opening of one RVV, causing a LOCA from the pressurizer to the containment. A loss of AC power was assumed at the same time, causing a loss of feedwater. Further, the RRVs were assumed to stuck in the closed position, preventing the return of the water from the containment to the reactor.

The reactor scram is triggered by high containment pressure at 2.2 s. The signal to open the RVVs and RRVs comes at 24 s from low pressurizer pressure. However, the RRVs fail to open in this scenario. The decay heat cannot be removed, and the coolant boils, decreasing the water level in the reactor (Fig. 8). The core uncover begins at about 5 h. The core uncover leads to cladding heat-up and oxidation, and later to core damage. All the water in the reactor has boiled in 40 h.

5.1. Progression of the accident, and numerical noise

Comparison of the results of different models is complicated by “numerical noise”, also called “numerical sensitivity” (Sandia, 2016; Chevalier & Sanchez, 2021; Sevón, 2024). Small differences in core component temperatures cause them to relocate at different times, after which the calculations start to bifurcate.

The numerical noise is illustrated in Fig. 9, which shows the hydrogen generation in five calculations with the base model. (Only three lines are visible because two pairs of the lines are very close to each other.) All the five calculations were made with the same input file, but random shuffling of the order of the flow paths was switched on by setting the sensitivity coefficient 4422(1) to 2.0. The order of the flow paths in the database is a purely numerical issue. Perturbing basically any input variable by a negligible amount produces similar numerical noise (Chevalier & Sanchez, 2021). The hydrogen generation is the same in all the five calculations until about 8 h, at which time the core materials begin to relocate and the results begin to bifurcate. The difference between the curves in Fig. 9 can be understood as the minimum amount of uncertainty. The full uncertainty, due to physical models in the code, is much larger than the numerical noise.

The numerical noise makes it more difficult to compare results of different models. Each calculation result is only one sample from a distribution caused by the numerical noise (Chevalier & Sanchez, 2021). If only one calculation is performed with two models, the difference between them is often numerical noise and not a real physical effect. In order to discern the possible “signal” from the noise, several calculations have to be performed with both models, adding small numerical

Fig. 10. Containment pressure in the SA scenario, base model, five calculations to show the numerical noise.

perturbations. The results have to be compared with statistical methods, to see if the difference between the models is greater than the noise. Note that numerical noise was not a problem for the DBA scenario because it did not lead to a change of the core geometry.

The containment pressure, calculated with the *base* model, is plotted in Fig. 10. Again, five calculations with random shuffling of the flow paths are shown because of the numerical noise. The pressure peaks at about 4.5 MPa during the blowdown period but decreases rapidly because the steam condenses on the containment walls. The pressure begins to increase again after 7 h, due to the hydrogen generation. The pressure remains high because the hydrogen cannot be removed from the containment. There is no oxygen that could react with the hydrogen. The numerical noise has a small effect on the containment pressure after the beginning of the core degradation at 8 h.

5.2. Effect of the containment and pool nodalization

The effect of the nodalization was investigated by calculating the severe accident scenario with the four nodalizations. Five calculations were performed with each of the four nodalizations, with random shuffling of the flow path order, in order to take into account the numerical noise. Five samples is considered as the minimum number for any statistical analyses, but more samples would offer better statistics. Five figures of merit were investigated:

1. Hydrogen generation in 168 h
2. Max containment pressure
3. Max containment pressure after core damage
4. Noble gas release to the environment in 168 h
5. Cs release to the environment in 168 h

The models of the containment and reactor pool should not have a significant effect on the hydrogen generation, so the first figure of merit is mainly a measure of the numerical noise. On the other hand, hydrogen generation does have a major effect on the containment pressure. The second figure of merit is the pressure peak during the blowdown, while the third one measures the longer-term pressurization due to hydrogen. The pressure after the core damage is important because it determines the containment leak rate and affects the fission product release to the environment.

The hydrogen generation, calculated with the four nodalizations, is presented in Fig. 11. The circles show the average result of the five

Fig. 11. Hydrogen generation in the SA scenario.

calculations with each nodalization. The black bars show the standard deviation, representing the numerical noise. The base model has less numerical noise than the three simpler nodalizations. It is uncertain if this is a real effect or a coincidence caused by the relatively small number of calculations.

The simpler nodalizations result in more hydrogen generation, on the average, than the base model. The statistical significance of the difference was investigated with the Student's *t*-test. The Excel function T.TEST was used, with two-tailed distribution and unequal variances between the data sets. The null hypothesis is that the different nodalizations would generate equally much hydrogen. The *t*-test could not reject the null hypothesis. The smallest P-value 0.063 is obtained for the 1-vol pool model, when compared with the base model. This can be interpreted as a 93.7 % probability that the null hypothesis can be rejected and that the 1-vol pool model generates more hydrogen than the base model. P-values less than 0.05 are generally considered statistically significant. Thus, the nodalization of the containment and the pool did not have a statistically significant effect on the hydrogen generation. This is in line with the physical understanding because the cladding oxidation occurs in the reactor, not in the containment.

The second figure of merit, maximum containment pressure, does not suffer from numerical noise because it occurs before the core

Fig. 12. Maximum containment pressure after core damage in the SA scenario.

damage. The result is $4.53 \text{ MPa} \pm 0.2 \%$ with all the four nodalizations. Hence, the nodalization of the containment and the pool did not affect the peak pressure.

The maximum containment pressure after core damage is presented in Fig. 12. Similarly to the hydrogen generation, the simpler nodalizations result in higher pressures than the base model, on the average. When analyzed with the statistical *t*-test, the difference between the 1-vol pool model and the base model is barely statistically significant, P-value 0.045. The pressure calculated with the 1-vol cont. and the 1-vol both models is not statistically significantly different from the base model.

The maximum containment pressure after core damage was analyzed further by investigating the correlation between the hydrogen generation and the pressure, shown in Fig. 13. As expected, there is a clear correlation because the containment is pressurized by the hydrogen. The *t*-test indicated that the 1-vol pool model might give statistically significantly higher pressures than the base model. However, Fig. 13 shows that the apparent difference is caused by the hydrogen generation, in which the difference was probably caused by numerical noise and not statistically significant.

The noble gas release to the environment is presented in Fig. 14. The release is determined by the containment leakage, so the results look similar to the containment pressure (Fig. 12). Again, the differences are

smaller than the numerical noise, so they are not statistically significant. The smallest P-value is 0.056 when comparing the 1-vol pool model to the base model. The plotted values are at the end of the calculations at 168 h, but the release continues indefinitely because the containment

Fig. 14. Noble gas release to the environment in 168 h.

Fig. 15. Cesium release to the environment.

Fig. 13. Maximum containment pressure after core damage, correlated with the hydrogen generation.

remains pressurized.

The cesium release to the environment is presented in Fig. 15. The Cs release has much more numerical noise than the noble gas release. With the base model, the standard deviation of the Cs release is 32 % of the average, while it was only 10 % for the noble gas release. The differences between the different nodalizations are much smaller than the numerical noise, and far from being statistically significant.

6. Conclusions

This study examined the effect of the nodalization of the containment and reactor pool when modeling a design basis accident and a severe accident scenario in an integral PWR using the MELCOR code. The base model had a relatively detailed nodalization, having 16 control volumes in the containment and 12 control volumes in the pool. Three simpler nodalizations were studied, modeling either the containment, the pool, or both with a single control volume.

The detailed nodalization resulted in some temperature stratification both in the containment and in the pool. However, the effect of the stratification on the pressures and the fission product releases was very small.

The only clear effect of the nodalization was seen during the blow-down phase of the DBA LOCA scenario. Modeling the containment with a single control volume gave slightly higher containment pressures than the more detailed nodalization. The reason was found to be the heat and mass transfer coefficients to the containment walls. The detailed nodalization generated a natural circulation in the containment, and the heat transfer mode was forced convection. On the contrary, in the single-volume containment, the flow velocity remained close to zero, the heat transfer mode was natural convection, and the heat transfer and condensation on the containment walls was less efficient.

In severe accident simulations, comparing the results is more difficult due to the numerical noise, caused by the core component relocation. Tiny differences in core component temperatures cause them to relocate at different times, after which the calculations start to bifurcate. Basically any change to the model causes visible changes to the results, but the change is often just numerical noise and not a real physical effect. In order to discern the effects of the nodalization from the noise, five calculations were performed with each nodalization. The only difference between the five calculations was random shuffling of the order of the flow paths in the code database. The magnitude of the numerical noise was assessed by the standard deviation among the five results with the same model. The statistical significance of the differences between the nodalizations was then investigated with the Student's *t*-test. The figures of merit were hydrogen generation, maximum containment pressure, and release of noble gases and Cs to the environment.

None of the differences between the nodalizations were found to be statistically significant. The lowest P-value, 0.045, was obtained when comparing the maximum containment pressure after core damage between the 1-vol pool model and the base model. Generally, P-values less than 0.05 are considered statistically significant. The average of the max pressures calculated by the 1-vol pool model was 6.4 % higher than with the base model. The standard deviation (due to the numerical noise) was 3.7 % of the average with the base model and 4.4 % with the 1-vol pool model. Thus, the difference between the nodalizations appears to be slightly greater than the numerical noise. However, upon closer investigation, it was found that the containment pressure is well correlated with the hydrogen generation. This is natural, since the containment is pressurized mainly by hydrogen. But physical understanding tells that the nodalization of the pool should not have a major effect on the

hydrogen generation in the reactor. And the difference in the hydrogen generation was not statistically significant, with the P-value of 0.063.

It is concluded that differences between single-volume and more detailed nodalizations of the containment and the reactor pool are relatively small. A detailed nodalization can simulate some temperature stratification, but the effect on pressures and fission product releases is probably not significant. Simple nodalizations are probably sufficient for most purposes when modeling accidents in an iPWR with a small submerged containment.

This study analyzed only two accident scenarios in one type of integral PWR with a partially submerged containment. It is possible that the nodalization would play a bigger role in some other accident scenario or some other iPWR design. In particular, if some accident scenario leads to a very strong stratification in the containment or the pool, the effect of the nodalization could be larger. However, such strong stratification scenarios were not found in the current project.

Declaration of competing interest

The author declares that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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